

Speculation on Gibbs' Paradox

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Gibb's paradox seems to arise when one considers an ideal gas of N particles, energy E , temperature T in a box of volume V and compares its entropy to two subsystems created by inserting a partition into the middle of the container without doing work. Each subsystem has $N/2$ particles, occupies $V/2$ and has $E/2$ and T . The issue is that one wishes to have $2S$ subsystem = S full system, i.e. to have entropy be extensive. To do so, a function of N is inserted into the entropy formula and it is argued that this has to do with identical particles and ultimately with quantum mechanics.

We argue that there seems to be a problem with this picture, namely the assignment of $N/2$ particles to each subsystem as this involves a measurement and hence changes entropy. To simplify matters, we consider a full system of 2 particles. Boltzmann's notion of entropy is $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$. Here the issue primarily seems to be with volume states, i.e. a particle can be in any tiny volume cell with equal probability. In the full V case, each of the two particles can be in any volume cell in V , but the same is true if one inserts a partition separating V into two $V/2$ cells. One cannot possibly know if one particle is in each cell unless one makes a measurement before inserting the partition and making a measurement changes entropy. When writing the number of states, these are probabilistic scenarios. It is possible that 2 particles are on one side of the partition and 0 on the other or 1 on each. The number of possible states for the partitioned system is the same as for the full volume. As a result, there is no paradox. There is only a paradox if one assumes that there is 1 particle on each side which is an assumption which cannot be made without making a measurement.

Entropy and Measurement

Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is based on probabilities $p(e_i)$ which means that there is uncertainty in a problem, i.e. one has not made measurements to resolve such an uncertainty. For example, for a coin toss, $p(\text{heads}) = p(\text{tails}) = .5$ and $S(\text{Shannon}) = -2 * .5 \ln(.5)$. If one measures the state of the tossed coin, then one knows it is heads (or tails) and so $p(\text{heads}) = 1$ or $p(\text{tails}) = 1$ and Shannon's entropy is 0. As a result, we suggest that one must be careful about assumed measurements that are implicitly made when considering entropy. We suggest that if one has a box of volume V containing N ideal gas particles and one places a partition in the middle, the statement that each side has $N/2$ gas particles must be based on a measurement and hence one is changing entropy by making such a measurement.

Entropy in an Ideal Gas

The Gibbs' paradox is primarily concerned with volume. One has an ideal gas of N particles in a container of volume V with T and E . One then places a partition in the middle, doing no work, and asserts that there are $N/2$ particles in each $V/2$ volume with T and $E/2$. One calculates the entropy of each $V/2$, $N/2$, system and argues that the sum of the two should equal the entropy of the full container. This requires inserting a factor which is a function of N in order to force

entropy to be extensive. It is then argued that this factor is based on indistinguishability and ultimately on quantum mechanics.

We suggest that one cannot possibly know how many particles are on each side of the partition without making a measurement. Such a measurement changes the value of entropy, we argue. We suggest that one must consider the system before and after the partition is added without any notion of measurement, i.e. without tampering with entropy. The counting of states is a statistical process.

In order to simplify our argument, we consider only two particles. The volume V is broken into equally sized tiny cells and each particle can occupy only one cell. One may consider all possible scenarios with two particles and the number of volume states should be proportional to:

$$V \cdot V \quad ((1))$$

In the case of a partition, one should also consider all possible volume states. One has no idea how many particles are on either side of the partition, i.e. there might be 2 on one side and 0 on the other or one on each, even if the particles are identical. As a result, one again has a total number of possible volume states of:

$$V \cdot V \text{ with a partition} \quad ((2))$$

In other words, the number of states and hence entropy of the two $V/2$ partitioned system is the same as that of the single V state automatically without having to insert any function of N factors or make any arguments about identical particles and quantum mechanics, we argue. In fact, there does not seem to be a Gibbs' paradox under this viewpoint.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that making a measurement on a system can affect the value of entropy. For example, the toss of a coin is associated with an entropy of $-2 \cdot 5 \ln(.5)$, while a measurement of the coin state leads to an entropy of 0. We suggest that one must be careful of scenarios which introduce implicit measurements when considering entropy as these actually change entropy. We argue that this seems to happen in the Gibbs' paradox case. One begins with an ideal gas with energy E , T , N particles in a volume V . It has a certain entropy S_{full} . One then inserts a partition in the middle of V without doing any work, breaking V into $V/2$ and $V/2$. It is then assumed that there are $N/2$ particles in each $V/2$ section. We argue that one cannot make this statement without making a measurement and this would affect entropy. One cannot possibly know how many particles are on each side. The counting of states is statistical scenario of all possible arrangements of particles.

We consider a simplified 2 particle scenario and argue that with and without the partition, there are the same number of volume states because each particle can sit in any dV . This leads to a total number of states of $V \cdot V$ for two particles regardless of whether there is a partition or not. The entropy with the partition is the same as the entropy without and there is no Gibbs' paradox. One does not need to insert any function of N and argue that it is due to identical particles and quantum mechanics. One simply cannot assume that there are $N/2$ particles in $V/2$ because in

counting states, this assumes a subset of volume states and implies that one has measured that there are in fact $N/2$ particles in each $N/2$, we argue.